

Quantification of Inherent Neutron Sources in Mixed Oxide Fuels by SOURCES 4C

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to fill the existing gap in the understanding of inherent neutron sources behavior in MOX fuels with high Pu content. Neutron emission rates from (α, n) reactions and spontaneous fission were analysed in different nuclear fuel compositions with the deterministic code SOURCES 4C. Fresh, aged, and irradiated fuels were considered. The results highlight strong variations in emission rates across compositions, with (α, n) reactions dominating in fresh MOX and spontaneous fission prevailing in fresh UO₂. For irradiated fuels, inherent neutron source rates strongly increase and spontaneous fission becomes the dominant contribution in all compositions. Key isotopic contributors were identified, and linear correlation coefficients are provided to support rapid first-order estimates of neutron source rates.

Keywords: Inherent neutron source, MOX fuel, (α, n) reaction, spontaneous fission, SOURCES 4C

1. INTRODUCTION

In the global push to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions and limit the global warming in line with the Paris Agreement, decarbonising the energy sector is crucial. Key climate roadmaps, such as the IEA Net Zero by 2050 Scenario, highlight the need for rapid deployment of low-carbon technologies, with nuclear power playing a key role in providing reliable baseload while renewable penetration increases. Within this framework, *newcleo* is actively developing lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs), aiming to improve fuel utilization, reduce high-level waste and enable closed fuel cycles.

In this context, it is critical to have solid, quantitative data about all inherent neutron sources in fuels under design or use, since these sources have an impact on safety and radiation protection, especially under accident or handling scenarios. While studies are present for molten salt reactor (MSR) concepts [1] and fresh MOX fuel with low Pu tenor [2], the literature reveals a gap regarding the inherent neutron source behavior of MOX fuels with high Pu content, particularly after irradiation in fast spectrum environments.

The present work addresses this gap by studying three fuel compositions - two distinct MOX fuels (one typical of PWR reactors [3], one typical of LFRs [4]) and a reference composition of UO₂ [5]. The nuclide inventory of the different fuels after being irradiated was calculated using the evolution code FISPACT II [6], and then SOURCES 4C [7] was employed to compute inherent neutron source rates arising from spontaneous fission and (α, n) reactions in both fresh and irradiated fuel. The metrics presented include total neutron emission rates for each fuel and nuclide-to-neutron rate correlations. These data aim to inform safety, radiation protection and licensing design for LFRs and Gen IV reactors, helping to ensure that, as nuclear contributes to zero-carbon energy, it does so with robust underlying data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology, including SOURCES 4C and FISPACT II theoretical recalls and fuel compositions considered; Section 3 reports the calculated neutron source rates and identifies major contributors, together with their nuclide-to-neutron yields; Section 4 summarizes the main findings and their implications for safe fuel handling and Gen IV reactors design.

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2. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology adopted to calculate the inherent neutron sources in different nuclear fuels. The approach combines isotopic inventory calculations and spontaneous fission and (α, n) source evaluation.

First, the main models implemented in SOURCES 4C for (α, n) and spontaneous fission neutron production are briefly recalled. Then, the fuel features and the irradiation model used to generate isotopic inventories with FISPACT II are presented. Finally, the main assumptions and limitations of the model are summarised.

2.1. SOURCES 4C - Theoretical Recalls

Inherent neutron sources originate from processes that occur spontaneously within matter, without the need for external irradiation. The dominant contributions arise from spontaneous fission and (α, n) reactions. In the latter case, alpha particles are generated by the decay of heavy isotopes and slowed down within the material. While slowing down, alpha particles may interact with light elements, producing neutrons. A further, though generally less significant, contribution could arise from the emission of delayed neutrons originating from the decay of fission products.

Various code have been specifically developed to quantify inherent neutron sources. Among these, SOURCES [7], a deterministic computer code developed to evaluate inherent neutron sources in oxide fuels, is capable of determining neutron production rates and energy spectra from (α, n) reactions, spontaneous fission and delayed neutron emission due to the decay of radionuclides in multiple configurations. In this work, version 4C of SOURCES is employed with the homogeneous media configuration, with a focus on neutron production from (α, n) reactions and spontaneous fission. Delayed neutron emission is not analysed, as its contribution is not observed in the calculations performed for the investigated cases.

To describe (α, n) reactions in homogeneous media, SOURCES includes a list of alpha emitting nuclei and, for each, a list of alpha emission lines with their relative intensity. The total rate of neutron emission in matter per unit time and volume from (α, n) reactions is

$$S^{(\alpha, n)} = \sum_k N_k \lambda_k \sum_l f_{kl}^\alpha P(E_0^{kl}), \quad (1)$$

where λ_k is the decay constant of the alpha emitting nuclide k , f_{kl}^α is the intensity of alpha line l in that nuclide and E_0^{kl} is the initial energy of the alpha particle from line l . $P(E_0^{kl})$ is the probability that an alpha particle with initial energy E_0^{kl} undergoes an (α, n) reaction before being stopped within the material,

$$P(E_0^{kl}) = \sum_i P_i(E_0^{kl}) = \sum_i \frac{N_i}{N} \int_0^{E_0^{kl}} dE \frac{\sigma_i(E)}{\varepsilon(E)}, \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_i(E)$ is the (α, n) reaction cross section of target nuclide i and $\varepsilon(E)$ is the material stopping cross section, i.e. the stopping power normalised by the atomic density,

$$\varepsilon = -\frac{1}{N} \frac{dE}{dx}. \quad (3)$$

Spontaneous fission is simply described by the neutron yield per unit time and volume,

$$S^{(SF)} = \sum_k N_k \lambda_k F_k^{SF} \bar{\nu}_k, \quad (4)$$

where F_k^{SF} is the branching ratio, namely the probability that a decay event is spontaneous fission, and $\bar{\nu}_k$ is the average number of neutrons emitted per spontaneous fission.

2.2. MOX Fuel Types

To compare inherent neutron emission in nuclear fuels, three distinct fuel compositions were considered: a reference UO_2 composition [5] and two different MOX fuels, one typical of PWRs [3] and one representative of LFRs [4]. The uranium and plutonium vectors used to describe the fuel are given in Table I. In UO_2 , the uranium isotopic concentrations are given for a 3 wt% enrichment in ^{235}U . For MOX fuels, two initial plutonium contents are considered to reflect typical compositions: 4 wt% and 7 wt% for the PWR-MOX, and 21.7 wt% and 27.8 wt% for the LFR-MOX.

Table I. Uranium vector and plutonium vector in the considered fuel compositions (wt%)

U Isotope	UO_2	PWR-MOX	LFR-MOX	Pu Isotope	MOX-PWR	MOX-LFR
^{234}U	0.0267	0.0012	0.003	^{238}Pu	2.5	2.3
^{235}U	3.0000	0.25	0.404	^{239}Pu	54.7	56.9
^{236}U	0.0138	0	0.010	^{240}Pu	26.1	27.0
^{238}U	96.9595	99.7488	99.583	^{241}Pu	9.5	6.1
				^{242}Pu	7.2	7.7

The evolution of the fuel composition throughout reactor operation was also investigated, with the aim of understanding how inherent neutron sources change compared to fresh fuel. For this purpose, irradiation cycles were simulated with FISPACT II, to follow the fuel isotopic changes with burn-up. Irradiation details are discussed in Sec. 2.3.

Although not ideal, nuclear fuel is often stored for a period before use. During this time, additional isotopes, such as ^{241}Am , may build up, which can significantly influence inherent neutron emission. To account for this effect, irradiation calculations were performed on both fresh fuel and fuel aged for a period of four years prior to irradiation, in order to simulate a realistic storage period before fuel utilization, which leads to the natural decay of some isotopes. The latter is referred to as "aged fuel".

2.3. FISPACT II and Irradiation History

FISPACT II [6] is an inventory code that solves the set of Bateman equations governing the time evolution of nuclide concentrations under irradiation. It employs the BDF (Backward Differentiation Formula) variant of the LSODE (Livermore Solver for Ordinary Differential Equations) solver, a stiff ODE solver with adaptive time-stepping to maintain numerical error below a user-defined threshold. The code can use a variety of evaluated nuclear data libraries for neutron cross sections and fission yields. In this work, constant power irradiation is considered, with power densities of 322 W/cm^3 and 380 W/cm^3 for the PWR and for the LFR fuel, respectively. The irradiation history consisted of five cycles of one year at full power (four cycles for the PWR case), each followed by a 30-day continuous outage to account for radioactive decay during shutdown. A simple sensitivity study was also performed by varying the power by $\pm 25\%$ to evaluate its impact on nuclide inventories and the resulting inherent neutron sources. The resulting time-dependent nuclide concentrations were subsequently used as input for the calculation of spontaneous fission and (α, n) source terms with SOURCES 4C. FISPACT II version 5.1 was employed for this study, using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library for neutron cross sections and fission yields.

2.4. Model Limitations

While SOURCES 4C is widely employed for inherent neutron source calculation, it still presents some limitations. These are in part related to the simplifying assumptions in the model, in part related to its nuclear data libraries. A critical discussion of these aspects is therefore essential.

For the purposes of the present work, the simplifying assumptions associated with treating the system as a homogeneous model do not represent a critical limitation, as the analysis is restricted to a qualitative comparison between fuel types, without reference to a specific geometry.

An important limitation of SOURCES 4C consists of its inability to evaluate neutron production from alpha particles with energies above 6.5 MeV. The code includes a list of 96 alpha emitting nuclides; among these, 22 have alpha emission lines exceeding this energy threshold. Therefore, such nuclides cannot be considered in SOURCES 4C simulations. This restriction arises from the lack of detailed (α, n) cross sections above 6.5 MeV. In principle, it could therefore be overcome by adopting more recent cross section evaluations (e.g., JENDL [8] or ENDF [9]).

Previous studies have already addressed this limitation by including alternative cross section libraries and extending the capabilities of the code beyond its original design (see, for example, [10]). However, in the present work the analysis is restricted to isotopes without alpha emission lines above 6.5 MeV, using the original version of the code, while the contribution of neglected isotopes is quantified separately.

3. RESULTS

This section presents the outcomes of the analyses described in Section 2. The results are structured to first provide the overall neutron source rates for each fuel type, followed by a description of the major nuclide contributors to spontaneous fission and (α, n) reactions.

3.1. Inherent neutron source rates

Inherent neutron source rates were evaluated using the deterministic code SOURCES 4C, assuming a homogeneous medium, for three different fuel compositions, namely UO_2 , PWR-MOX and LFR-MOX, where the MOX fuel could have different Pu contents. For each fuel composition, four different cases were considered.

Fig. 1 provides a comparison between all the analysed compositions in the four cases considered: fresh fuel (a), aged fuel (b), fresh fuel after irradiation (at nominal power) (c), aged fuel after irradiation (d), i.e. fuel that was first aged for four years and then irradiated. Results clearly show that inherent neutron emission strongly depends on the fuel composition, leading to variations in the neutron yield of several orders of magnitude. Of particular importance is the plutonium content: as it increases, so does the neutron yield. Moreover, the presence of plutonium leads to (α, n) reactions being the dominant contribution in fresh MOX fuel, conversely to fresh UO_2 in which spontaneous fission prevails. This difference arises from the presence of strong alpha emitters, namely ^{238}Pu , ^{239}Pu , ^{240}Pu . Additionally, the total neutron yield and the relative contributions from (α, n) reactions and spontaneous fission vary significantly across the fuel life cycle. It can be observed that after irradiation inherent neutron source rates strongly increase, with spontaneous fission becoming the dominant contribution. Such a trend is consistent with expectations, since irradiation results in the accumulation of isotopes characterised by significant spontaneous fission rates. It is also worth noticing that no significant differences are introduced in UO_2 by the four-year-aging, as no isotope with relevant activity is present among its decay products. In aged MOX fuels, conversely, the total neutron production slightly increases. In particular, neutrons from (α, n) reactions increase due to the production of isotopes from the decay of plutonium, e.g. ^{241}Am , while the spontaneous fission contribution marginally decreases. No contribution from delayed neutron emission is observed in any of the cases investigated. Delayed neutron precursors are absent in fresh fuel, as they are produced during irradiation. However, precursors are characterised by short half-lives, undergoing complete decay within the 30-day outage period. Consequently, also the analysis of fuel compositions following irradiation shows no contribution from delayed neutron emission.

Figure 1. Inherent neutron source in units of neutrons/cm³/s from (α, n) reactions and from spontaneous fission (SF) in the analysed fuel compositions for four different cases: fresh fuel (a), four-year-aged fuel (b), fuel after irradiation (c), aged fuel after irradiation (d). For irradiated fuels, different power levels are considered.

The evolution of the fuel isotopic composition under irradiation was analysed at different power levels, specifically within a $\pm 25\%$ interval around nominal power. Fig. 2 shows inherent neutron source rates for UO₂, PWR-MOX with 7 wt% Pu and LFR-MOX with 27.8 wt% Pu after irradiation at the different power densities. As expected, higher power densities yield a larger increase in the inherent neutron source. It should also be noted that the relative contribution of spontaneous fission shows a modest increase with power density.

3.2. Identification of Key Contributors to Inherent Neutron Sources

The contributions of individual nuclides to the total inherent neutron source were analysed to identify those isotopes that give a higher contribution and correlate nuclide concentrations with the corresponding neutron emission rates.

For (α, n) reactions, we can distinguish between "source" isotopes, which decay producing an alpha particle, and "target" isotopes, light isotopes on which (α, n) reactions occur. In fresh fuel, oxygen is the only target nuclide, so it accounts for all (α, n) neutrons. After irradiation additional light isotopes are produced in small amounts, but oxygen remains by far the main contributor. In particular, about 90% is produced by ¹⁸O and about 8% by ¹⁷O. The important "source" isotopes, conversely, change with fuel composition and irradiation state. In fresh UO₂, about 80% of neutrons come from ²³⁴U, even though its concentration is relatively small, while in fresh MOX fuel, most neutrons are produced by ²³⁸Pu. An additional contribution from ²⁴¹Am arises in aged MOX fuel. After irradiation, neutron production from (α, n) reactions is dominated by ²⁴²Cm in both UO₂ and MOX. Considering spontaneous fission, all neutrons are produced by ²³⁸U in fresh UO₂, while in fresh MOX fuel the dominant contributors are ²⁴⁰Pu (about 60%), ²⁴²Pu and ²³⁸Pu. After irradiation, spontaneous fission is dominated by ²⁴²Cm and

Figure 2. Inherent neutron source in units of neutrons/cm³/s from (α, n) reaction and from spontaneous fission (SF) in the analysed fuel compositions after irradiation at different power densities.

²⁴⁴Cm in all compositions.

Figure 3 presents scatter plots of the simulation results discussed in the previous sections, showing nuclide concentration versus neutron emission rate for spontaneous fission and (α, n) reactions. The plots include the isotopes generating at least the 1% of either the (α, n) or the spontaneous fission neutron source rate in at least one of the cases analysed, highlighting the dominant nuclides responsible for neutron production.

From these analyses, it emerges that the correlation between the concentration of key nuclides and neutron emission, for both (α, n) and spontaneous fission, is linear, with values R^2 consistently higher than 0.99. Lower R^2 values are observed for (α, n) reactions on fission-product targets, such as ¹³C or ¹⁹F. This indicates that, independent of the type of nuclear fuel considered, these correlations can be used to obtain a simple, yet reasonably accurate estimate of the inherent neutron source rates. Based on the linear coefficients $a_k^{(\alpha,n)}$ and a_k^{SF} from Table II, the total neutron source rates were recalculated as

$$S = \sum_k (a_k^{(\alpha,n)} + a_k^{SF}) N_k, \quad (5)$$

where the coefficients represent the proportionality factors between nuclide concentrations and neutron emission rates. This reconstruction yielded relative errors consistently below 1% for both (α, n) and

Figure 3. Inherent neutron source from (α, n) reactions (left) for fixed source-target nuclide couples and from spontaneous fissions (right) for fixed source nuclides.

spontaneous fission.

Table II. Linear coefficients, in units s^{-1} , relating nuclide concentrations in $\frac{\text{atom}}{\text{barn}\cdot\text{cm}}$ to neutron source rates for (α, n) and spontaneous fission.

Isotope	$a_k^{(\alpha, n)}$	a_k^{SF}
Am241	1.102E+06	4.961E+02
Cm242	1.535E+09	7.905E+09
Cm244	3.212E+07	4.473E+09
Pu238	5.498E+06	1.028E+06
Pu239	1.566E+04	5.903E+00
Pu240	5.843E+04	4.165E+05
Pu242	8.503E+02	6.953E+05
U234	1.200E+03	2.665E+00
U235	2.664E-01	4.064E-03
U238	3.366E-02	5.385E+00

The near-linear correlation observed between nuclide concentration and neutron emission rate can be understood from the governing relation for (α, n) emission (Eq. 1). The emission rate is essentially proportional to the concentration of the alpha-emitting nuclides, N_k , which constitute the dominant varying factor in the expression. While the concentration of target nuclides, N_i , also evolves during irradiation, in the fuels considered oxygen represents by far the target that contributes to neutron emission the most, and it undergoes only minor relative variations over the fuel cycle, so its concentration can be treated as constant. A further source of non-linearity lies in the material stopping cross section $\epsilon(E)$, which depends on the overall composition of the material. However, in practice, the stopping power does not change significantly with the relatively small variations in composition typical of the cases considered, and its effect on the neutron emission rate can be considered as negligible. As a result, neutron emission is nearly proportional to the alpha-emitter concentration.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to fill the existing gap in the understanding of inherent neutron source behaviour in MOX fuels with high Pu content. Neutron emission rates from (α, n) reactions and spontaneous fission were analysed for different fuel compositions using the deterministic code SOURCES 4C. Two MOX fuels were considered (one typical of PWR reactors and one typical of LFRs), alongside a reference UO_2

composition. For each case, the analysis accounted for isotopic evolution after an aging period as well as after irradiation at different power levels.

The results show that inherent neutron emission rates strongly depend on the fuel composition, spanning several orders of magnitude across the cases considered. The neutron emission rate was found to increase with power density and with plutonium content. In fresh MOX fuels, (α, n) reactions provide a significant share of the total neutron production, whereas in fresh UO_2 spontaneous fission dominates. The build-up of ^{241}Am during aging was shown to increase the overall emission rates for MOX fuels. After irradiation, the neutron yield increases substantially for all fuels, with spontaneous fission becoming the prevailing source.

The key isotopes contributing to neutron emission, both from (α, n) reactions and spontaneous fission, were identified and analysed in order to establish a correlation between nuclide concentrations and the corresponding neutron emission rates. The list of the main contributing isotopes was found to vary with fuel type (MOX or UO_2) and irradiation state, but not with plutonium content or with irradiation power level. A near-linear correlation between the concentration of nuclides and the neutron emission rate was found when analysing isotopes generating at least 1% of the total neutron emission from (α, n) reactions or spontaneous fission in at least one of the cases analysed. Nuclide-to-neutron yields are provided, which can be used to perform quick first-order estimates of neutron emission rates.

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